

Knowledge organisation and intelligent R&D for chemicals and materials industries – A workshop report

Gerhard Goldbeck^{1,2*}, Vikki Cantrill¹, Ferry Kienberger³, and Alexandra Simperler²

¹ Goldbeck Consulting Ltd, UK

² EMMC ASBL - European Materials Modelling Council, Belgium

³ Keysight, Austria

* Corresponding Author: gerhard@goldbeck-consulting.com

Contents

Contents.....	2
Preface	3
Introduction	3
Industry perspectives.....	3
Lessons learnt from collaborative research projects.....	6
More semantics, AI, and EMMO	7
Looking to the future of intelligent R&D	8
Key points.....	8
Semantic data management maturity is low, but substantial advances are planned.....	8
Improve data health and semantics at the data source	9
“Digital scientist” interacts with multiple electronic and digital systems	9
Interoperability is the least addressed of the FAIR principles	9
Development of common semantics in materials industry	10
Between promise and reality, agentic AI and ontologies	10
Acknowledgements.....	10
Disclaimer.....	10
Workshop contributions	10
References	11

Preface

This report provides some reflections on the presentations and discussions that took place during the Semantic Materials Workshop 2025 on 10 November 2025 at Homerton College, Cambridge, UK, with 38 in-person and 35 online registered participants. The workshop was organised by Semantic Materials¹, the semantic technologies branch of Goldbeck Consulting Ltd², in collaboration with European Materials Modelling Council³ (EMMC) and the DigiCell project^{4,5}.

This report is an appraisal of the event and not an accurate summary of presentations or discussion contributions.

Introduction

The workshop followed on from the Semantic Materials Workshop 2024⁶, which took place in April 2024 in London. The objective of this second workshop was to share advances, needs, challenges, and experiences in different fields when using semantic technologies and artificial intelligence (AI) and compare and contrast changes in this area since the first workshop. From a European perspective, use cases, lessons learnt and the foundations of semantic technologies within the chemicals and materials sectors were presented and practical solutions shared.

Semantic Materials¹ conducted a maturity study⁷ and the preliminary results show that materials industries are aware of semantic data management methods and plan to or are carrying out pilot projects. Significant shifts and changes in the adoption of AI and knowledge management technologies are expected in the next three to five years as these methods become operational and are rolled out across organisations.

It is important to understand the complexity and variety of materials that industry deals with. For example, a simple item, like a palm-sized cogwheel, may be a well-defined alloy yet comprise a vast number of microstructures that can alter its macroscopic behaviour. This calls for multiscale modelling and characterisation^{8,9} that demands and produces a plethora of data that then often relies on human experts for correct interpretation.

Materials science lacks agreed terminologies and controlled vocabularies for semantics¹⁰. In contrast, chemistry can draw on the IUPAC Gold Book¹¹ for terminology. To address the issue, Semantic Materials¹ brings together experts from philosophy, physics, chemistry and materials sciences that strives to put the field on a sound ontological footing and provide knowledge translators to benefit industry.

Industry perspectives

The **pharmaceutical industry** collects vast amounts of data. To be useful to people and for AI, all data assets must have meaning and provenance with no ambiguity. Then, solutions, such as knowledge graphs, can enable staff to explore particular data spaces. To succeed, FAIR data¹²⁻¹⁴ is needed from the outset, which relies on data producers trained on data compliance.

It is advisable to start by building small data models that describe a specific entity and can be pulled into an application ontology. This, subsequently, serves as reference model, which describes all entities within research and development (R&D) of an organisation. Controlled vocabularies should be built so that data producers label each entity consistently, as well as using alternative/subject-specific labels and hidden labels^{15,16}, for example the National Cancer Institute Thesaurus¹⁷. In combination with Persistent Unique Identifiers (PIDs)¹⁸, this provides a set of metadata that implement FAIR principles in practice and generates a semantic structure for data specialists that are largely invisible to the data users.

As a result, data consumers profit from catalogues using Uniform Resource Identifier¹⁹ on data assets and metadata that improve interoperability due to data dictionaries based on the above controlled vocabularies and reference models. These help to explain what each data column is and how it is aligned into a data model. This sort of data management forms the majority of a data scientists' work, so improving interoperability can notably reduce IT costs. R&D scientists' appreciation of interoperability as an asset beyond their project will further improve data management across the organisation and importantly make deployment of AI across an organisation much more efficient.

This process is best described as "putting the knowledge graph into the data". So, when data scientists build their data asset, they also catalogue it by following an information standard and simultaneously develop a data dictionary. As and when data scientists find terms that are not in the controlled vocabularies, such terms should be highlighted to the respective developer teams. By following these rigorous workflows data assets fit for AI can be produced. It takes considerable time and effort to develop such systems, so their development may also benefit from pre-competitive collaborations²⁰.

From a semantics and knowledge management perspective, the **materials industry** is very broad and complex. For example, several raw materials may undergo several processes/formulations to give a new product that is sold only to become the starting point for the next organisation in the value chain. Consequently, numerous testing and characterisation techniques are used with a plethora of data formats and subject/domain-specific conventions, which hinder the realisation of FAIR¹² data. The resulting data is usually not reusable or interoperable, hence extracting knowledge from it can then require considerable time and effort.

In an effort to advance digitalisation, companies have introduced a wide range of systems and tools, including report archives; electronic lab notebooks (ELNs)²¹; laboratory information management systems²²; scientific data management systems (that scrape data from testing rigs and analytical equipment into repositories); modelling and simulation tools and related data systems; environmental, health, and safety software; and enterprise resource planning²³ systems. Given the complexity of industrial materials R&D, projects can involve many of the above. However, this approach can be at odds with the researcher, who often likes to try numerous ways to solve a problem, which don't readily fit into the systems provided. For example, if entering each of these experiments into a system triggers several levels of authorisation, researchers may opt for traditional note taking and log only selected successful experiments, without realising the onward impact of the information/knowledge lost. The situation persists because the materials industry does not have the

same regulatory requirements as pharma and life sciences areas have that incentivises more standardised ways of knowledge organisation.

Yet, the materials industry is well aware of importance of FAIR data and metadata; however, semantics is abstract to many research scientists who lack knowledge to its potential benefits. Interoperability is not considered a priority because the field is very broad and many research areas have been able to thrive without extensive knowledge management. A way forward here could be to encourage people think about the data and information they get from outside/other domains and how that could be incorporated.

The experience with AI tools so far is that they are often overpromoted as able to extract information from any data. There is an opportunity for semantic data experts to raise awareness, demystify AI and how it best works in combination with FAIR data. However, more user-friendly tools and interfaces will be required to entice scientists to adopt semantic technologies.

An example from the **aerospace industry** demonstrates the benefit of semantic technologies to support the industry's sustainability objectives. Although the recycling of metal parts, such as aluminium, is quite successful, composite materials are often incinerated for energy recovery or end up in landfill. New generation aircraft will comprise thermoplastics that are recyclable and can end up again within the sector^{24,25}. To support this, the researchers gathered key data on the materials features and properties, and process parameters along with information from literature, databases, modelling software and lab tests, so that they could identify optimal recycled blends for materials. However, composites are not uniform, so data on the thermoplastic, reinforcement fibres, defects, and so on needs to be included, which adds to the complexity of the problem. This challenge was addressed by using a knowledge graph in conjunction with a bespoke ontology that covered "product" and "process". In the graph logical model each node was a product and each relationship between nodes a process. Data was extracted automatically with a Named Entity Recognition model to automatically identify and classify entities.

Battery development and production is an example of an "everything problem" that requires linked knowledge across many domains to solve it; hence interoperability is essential.

All data generated and used must be high quality because end users rely on its accuracy. In this industry sector semantic knowledge organisation is used in individual and hierarchical data models with an emphasis on metadata integration so data can be used across the divisions of an organisation or between scientific disciplines. EU project DigiCell^{4,5} looks at the characterisation of materials, such as lithium-iron phosphate and lithium-ion nickel, manganese and cobalt batteries. The project aims to test batteries accurately through physical electrochemical models and create digital twins. Such batteries must also follow the international ISO²⁶ and electro technical standardisation²⁷ to be deployed globally and work safely in a variety of devices.

Instruments need to be well calibrated so that each measurement is accurate and reliable, so metrology plays an important role, which makes hardware expensive. Therefore, digital twins can be more economical for the battery and for the environment it operates in. Digital twins in the battery sector include characterisation of surfaces, 3D finite element method and 3D scanning electron

microscopy, electron microscopy and tomography. This led to the development of the Battery Testing Ontology (BTO)²⁸, which provides a comprehensive framework that represent data and protocols in battery testing and quality control. The BTO is fully aligned with the Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology (EMMO).²⁹ Sometimes an ontology can help with knowledge organisation and sometimes a large language model (LLM) is sufficient. For example, batteries in electric cars need to be connected to a national power grid to charge. The regulations that need to be followed to do so can be retrieved by a LLM and the information gathered used to automate tests to ensure compliance with regulations in different countries.

The interoperability efforts in the battery field have been supported by a range of European **research projects** that actively develop and use semantic technologies³⁰. This approach can result in a digital twin that acts as a coherent and persistent framework for linking (data) assets. EU project BIG-MAP^{31,32} and Battery2030+³³ developed the Battery Interface Ontology (BattINFO)³⁴, a semantic resource with essential terms and relationships to describe battery cells, materials, methods, and data. BattINFO is an extension of the EMMO²⁹, adheres to World Wide Web Consortium³⁵ best practices and offers a collection of concepts to describe battery knowledge that build on International Electrotechnical Commission standards²⁷ and the IUPAC Gold Book¹¹. BattINFO³⁴ enables linking of data from and across research data and other prominent sources, such as Wikidata³⁶, DBpedia³⁷ and Pubchem³⁸. A researcher can also retrieve additional information on chemicals from InChI³⁹ keys and CAS registry⁴⁰ numbers. BattINFO includes Schema.org⁴¹ markup for semantic web integration to enable results from the Google Knowledge Graph⁴² and Google⁴³.

Such a foundational resource enables practical implementations that address challenges such as interoperability of timeseries test data from different equipment providers, and the exchange of model parameters between different battery simulation packages.

Ultimately, BattINFO is an open-source battery knowledge base that consolidates data sets, metadata and semantic technology to create a coherent and persistent description of battery resources.

Lessons learnt from collaborative research projects

When working collaboratively on publicly funded projects, it is essential that there is a clear and detailed data management plan that all partners adopt and conform to. The plan should follow the data lifecycle: planning, acquisition, analysis, preservation, sharing, and reuse of data and be sufficiently detailed to ensure it is instructive.

Data is often acquired as an Excel or csv file. Consequently, data analysis requires better tooling so workflows and data provenance can be conserved, which are key for reusability and interoperability. Tools, like ELNs, help but effort is needed to understand and record metadata. From the start, data stewards need to assist data producers to create FAIR data. To support that effort, semantic technologies need to be implemented and ready to use for data producers from the start.

More semantics, AI, and EMMO

The UK is building an infrastructure for **physical sciences research data**, called the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI)⁴⁴. The metadata in the PSDI is organised into resource themes that groups data services, tools and guidance that is searchable across all data sources. Metadata⁴⁵ is crucial and uses one common language to cover all the physical sciences. The infrastructure started very recently and a simple technology stack is available. PSDI takes a top-down approach, starting with metadata about resources [based on the Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT)]⁴⁶ and then tackles metadata about the data or data provenance metadata. The approach is based on the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework⁴⁷ — a set of principles and domain-agnostic standards to support FAIR data interoperability.

Agentic AI aims to achieve autonomous, goal-oriented decision-making and actions. Within materials science such a system could identify a new material with desired properties and then generate the necessary code for robots to go ahead and make. This would supersede people writing code on systems that have little or no autonomy. Agentic AI systems work optimally when context is provided, and knowledge graphs are a good way to do this.

For example, a multi-agent system could optimise how a task is done by using graphing methods. For R&D, this could create a kind of “autonomous scientist” in which an LLM extracts data from thousands of scientific papers and creates a well-structured knowledge graph. There might be an ontologist agent monitoring nodes and relationships, defining terms or cleaning the ontology. There could be scientific and reviewer agents then deployed to discover a new material.

Applying agentic AI to robots requires careful consideration. Once the robot is given a task, it acts. The action must be right the first time or there could be serious consequences. As a safeguard, the coding agent can be provided with a machine-readable “policy card” to encode laws, regulations, ethics and policies. Ontologies can form the foundations for such agentic AI guardrails.

Since 2018, a team of scientists have been developing the **EMMO**²⁹ to build a knowledge framework able to represent the materials world including its physics foundations. Existing top-level ontologies did not satisfy conceptualisations from the applied sciences. For example, quantum phenomena were absent and relativity ignored. So, they developed a multiscale and multiphysics approach to represent entities and their interactions and interrelations, from a very fundamental “micro-physics” level up to a macroscopic level. As a result, EMMO provides a common language that is able to express all aspects of the material world in a way that is consistent with a scientific world view.

What are the **best practices** to implement **semantic technologies**? We need to start small and gradually build up semantic models and data integration of the processes a client uses and the materials involved. Data is typically logged in different systems; perhaps paper records were digitised and evolved over time. Both processes and systems will have evolved over time, so managing the various data can become complicated. Here, knowledge graphs facilitate linked data and enable clients to query it. However, proof of concept is needed to demonstrate the value of bringing data together in the first place. During implementation, case models are essential to check the validity and ease-of-use of what is being introduced. Easy user interfaces are often preferable to SPARQL⁴⁸ queries

for clients. Once a client understands that semantic technologies can bring efficiencies, next a developer can identify other questions users might want to query data on and expand the model stepwise. In relation to problem solving, semantic technologies can find issues faster so “time-out-of-market” can be reduced, the latter being an important business factor.

Looking to the future of intelligent R&D

Researchers readily engage with AI projects, but less so with semantics or data governance, which are vital for more intelligent R&D. Interest in this fundamental intelligence work needs to be encouraged in such a way that people want to take ownership of it and be actively involved. For example, a data expert identifies a query that is notoriously slow due to lack of interoperability and produces a case study to demonstrate the benefits semantics bring. Semantics also add a level of confidence to an answer because queries can be guided by established facts.

LLMs work with text and rely on language to describe the world, whereas sciences use mathematics and data. Here, the epistemological limit of LLMs can hinder scientific advances and interactions without supportive semantics^{49,50}. Scientists also move on to new fields relatively frequently, which would necessitate retraining an LLM. Here, a decent foundational ontology would facilitate moves to new topic areas.

Having a common semantic reference is seen as highly valuable in the above contexts. A number of fields including pharmaceuticals and life sciences benefit from many years of joint efforts on ontologies. In contrast, currently, there has been much less incentive for materials and manufacturing to work on common ontologies because the breadth of materials science means limited topic overlap. An exception to this is the battery sector that, owing to a series of EU projects^{33,51}, can use semantics and ontologies for intelligent R&D.

Now may be the right moment for materials science field to agree on and establish a common semantic basis, as a number of factors align: the need for data integration across domain, functions and value chains is ever increasing; according to the Gartner hype cycle⁵², knowledge graphs as a technology sector have entered a mature and more productive state of development; the synergy between AI/LLMs and semantics is well established (ontologies improve AI results and vice versa, AI/LLMs can be used to speed-up ontology development and improve useability), and due to the EMMO and its ecosystem of discipline and domain ontologies — such as the Characterisation Methodology Domain Ontology⁵³ — there is a strong semantic foundation.

Key points

Semantic data management maturity is low, but substantial advances are planned

Preliminary results of the Semantic Materials maturity survey⁷ are:

- Current situation is the maturity is close to level 2: “Active”, meaning there are experimental or pilot projects but there is no or little operational implementation in business functions.
- Organisations aim to lift their maturity to between levels 3 and 4 across People, Processes, Data and Tools and Technologies, which means operations with clear objectives and

implementation in some functions, working towards systemic, robust and scalable implementations across the business.

- The biggest issues organisations aim to address are data from several functional areas that need to be manually collected and integrated; no common definitions of business relevant data and fields used by multiple functional areas; and several “versions” of similar data exist across systems and functional areas. So ultimately, it is unclear what the source of truth is.

Improve data health and semantics at the data source

Generally, the labelling of experimental data produced is of relatively poor standard. This means the barrier to achieve FAIR data, in particular interoperability, is insurmountable. Efforts to address the issue include:

- Ensure data are assigned PIDs.
- Catalogue data by using established metadata standards, such as DCAT⁴⁶.
- Establish and use controlled vocabularies and data dictionaries.

These efforts can be referred to as “put the knowledge graph into the data” rather than “put the data into the knowledge graph”. Don’t defer proper metadata until the point of data integration, rather work with the data producers to ensure good “data health” to enable linked data.

“Digital scientist” interacts with multiple electronic and digital systems

The efforts for FAIR data and digitalisation have led to the introduction of a wide range of systems and tools. However, the introductions of more and more systems, each with their own requirements to use them, is not compatible with R&D working practices. Although each system claims to make data FAIR, often they create more metadata siloes, unless there is adequate central management of metadata, dictionaries and ontologies.

Interoperability is the least addressed of the FAIR principles

The main goal of interoperability principle in FAIR data is to provide a “common understanding” of digital objects by means of a language for knowledge representation to be used to represent these objects⁵⁴. By definition, interoperability involves different systems and/or functions, so it tends to be overlooked and is the least addressed of the FAIR principles.

At the same time, strategic R&D needs interoperability even though existing tools struggle. Well-documented, shared semantics (controlled vocabularies, metadata schema, ontologies) is key to overcoming interoperability issues. Linked data opens up resources, for example, interoperability between test data from different equipment providers.

Development of common semantics in materials industry

The challenge is that materials science is very broad, so it is difficult to gather sufficient interest in collaborating on common vocabularies and ontologies. Any developments must be understandable, usable, and universal; they need to integrate with different types of software and systems.

In industrial materials R&D, it is not clear that there will be a standout application for semantic technologies of business value. People matter more than platforms, hence there is a need to work with subject matter experts and their networks to demonstrate value.

Between promise and reality, agentic AI and ontologies

There have been substantial advances in materials discovery by using AI in general and agentic AI in particular. Hundreds of millions of Euros of venture capital are being invested in the sector^{55,56}. And as momentum grows within this area, the limitations of LLMs and the role of ontologies are becoming clearer. Some of the points discussed include:

- Agents need to extract large amounts of data, but underlying, well-organised ontologies for concepts can give higher quality information because natural language tends to be imprecise.
- The use of LLMs to query graphs provides context and helps to avoid hallucinations.
- LLMs are based on text and language, whereas science uses mathematics and images to describe the world. So, developers need to be aware of the possible epistemological limits of LLMs due to the language that is used to represent the world.
- Ontologies that express our scientific world understanding, such as EMMO, with LLM-friendly documentation will be valuable assets to AI agents.

Acknowledgements

This study has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement no. 101135486 (DigiCell) and no. 101137725 (BatCAT), and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10091190]. The Semantic Materials Workshop 2025 was kindly supported by the EMMC³ and Semantic Partners⁵⁷. We are grateful for the insights and information from all of the contributors to the Semantic Materials Workshop 2025.

Disclaimer

All statements of fact, opinion, or analysis expressed in the report are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the contributors to the workshop or of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The information used and statements of fact made are not guarantees, warranties or representations as to their completeness or accuracy. The authors assume no liability for any short term or long term decision made by any reader based on analysis included in this report. In many cases, the opinion expressed in the reports is our current opinion based on prevailing trends and is subject to change.

Workshop contributions

The workshop was held on Monday, 10th November 2025, in Cambridge, UK. The following presentations took place:

From putting the data into the graph to putting the graph into the data – Delivering ontology-based data management by Ben Gardener, AstraZeneca, UK.

Building knowledge organisation in materials-based industries: requirements, challenges and experiences by Ed Wright, Johnson Matthey, UK.

A flowchart methodology for extracting, structuring, and standardising materials and processes data from text by Anaële Lefeuvre and Julien Gosteau, Airbus, France.

From battery manufacturing to power-grid emulations: Data analytics, ontologies, and AI by Ferry Kienberger, Keysight, Austria.

A semantic approach to battery digital twins by Simon Clark, SINTEF, Norway.

Lessons learnt in materials semantic representation by Gerhard Goldbeck, Semantic Materials, UK.

How are we standardising metadata in the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI)? by Aileen Day, University of Southampton, UK.

The future of Agentic AI: From knowledge graphs to autonomous research agents with a focus on materials science by Juraj Mavračić, Symbiotic Dynamics, UK.

EMMO: foundations and core principles by Emanuele Ghedini, University of Bologna, Italy.

Semantic technologies best practice implementations, experiences from projects by James Lawrence, Semantic Partners, UK.

There was also a panel discussion entitled Intelligent chemicals and materials R&D: Combining neural and symbolic AI.

References

1. Semantic Materials website. <https://semanticmaterials.com/>.
2. Materials Modelling website. <https://materialsmodelling.com/> (2025).
3. The European Materials Modelling Council website. <https://emmc.eu/>.
4. DigiCell – Battery Material Characterisation and Digital Twins for Cell to Pack Performance in Agile Manufacturing Pilot Lines and Automotive Field | DigiCell. <https://www.digicell-project.eu/>.
5. Battery Material Characterisation And Digital Twins For Cell To Pack Performance In Agile Manufacturing Pilot Lines And Automotive Field | DigiCell | Project. *CORDIS | European Commission*
<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101135486>.
6. Cantrill, V., de Baas, A., Roscioni, O. M. & Goldbeck, G. *Developing Ontologies in Materials Science*.
<https://zenodo.org/records/11127892> (2024) doi:10.5281/zenodo.11127892.
7. Cantrill, V. Semantic Data Management Maturity Assessment Service. *Semantic Materials*
<https://semanticmaterials.com/semantic-data-maturity-service/> (2025).

8. Roscioni, O. M. Managing the complexity of multiscale modelling with semantic technologies. (2025)
doi:10.5281/zenodo.14782279.
9. Terkaj, W., Qi, Q., Urgo, M., Scott, P. J. & Jiang, X. Multi-scale modelling of manufacturing systems using ontologies and delta-lenses. *CIRP Annals* **70**, 361–364 (2021).
10. Medina-Smith, A. *et al.* A Controlled Vocabulary and Metadata Schema for Materials Science Data Discovery. *Data Science Journal* **20**, 18 (2021).
11. *The IUPAC Compendium of Chemical Terminology: The Gold Book*. (International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC), Research Triangle Park, NC, 2025). doi:10.1351/goldbook.
12. Amdouni, E. & Jonquet, C. FAIR or FAIRer? An integrated quantitative FAIRness assessment grid for semantic resources and ontologies. *15th International Conference on Metadata and Semantics Research (MISR 2021)* (Madrid, Spain, 2021).
13. Brinson, L. C. *et al.* Community action on FAIR data will fuel a revolution in materials research. *MRS Bulletin*
<https://doi.org/10.1557/s43577-023-00498-4> (2023) doi:10.1557/s43577-023-00498-4.
14. Adamovic, N. *et al.* Semantic Knowledge Management for Materials: the benefits of a FAIR data and model-based approach in industrial research and development. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13304676>
(2024) doi:10.5281/ZENODO.13304676.
15. SKOS Simple Knowledge Organization System Reference. <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/>.
16. SKOS eXtension for Labels (SKOS-XL) Namespace Document. <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/skos-xl.html>.
17. National Cancer Institute Thesaurus | NCBO BioPortal. <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/NCIT>.
18. What are persistent identifiers (PIDs)? *ORCID* <https://support.orcid.org/hc/en-us/articles/360006971013-What-are-persistent-identifiers-PIDs>.
19. Uniform Resource Identifier. *Wikipedia*
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Uniform_Resource_Identifier&oldid=1320412352 (2025).
20. Pistoia Alliance website. <https://www.pistoiaalliance.org/>.
21. Electronic lab notebook. *Wikipedia*
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Electronic_lab_notebook&oldid=1314203028 (2025).

22. Laboratory information management system. *Wikipedia*
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Laboratory_information_management_system&oldid=1309322724 (2025).
23. Enterprise resource planning. *Wikipedia*
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Enterprise_resource_planning&oldid=1322756638 (2025).
24. Toray Advanced Composites and Partners Launch End-of-Life Aerospace Recycling Program. *Plastics Today*
<https://www.plasticstoday.com/automotive-mobility/toray-advanced-composites-daher-and-tarmac-aerosave-launch-joint-end-of-life-aerospace-recycling-program>.
25. Ramawat, N., Sharma, N., Yamba, P. & Sanidhi, M. A. T. Recycling of polymer-matrix composites used in the aerospace industry-A comprehensive review. *Materials Today: Proceedings*
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2023.05.386> (2023) doi:10.1016/j.matpr.2023.05.386.
26. ISO - International Organization for Standardization. *ISO* <https://www.iso.org/home.html> (2025).
27. IEC website. <https://www.iec.ch/homepage>.
28. Del Nostro, P. *et al.* Battery testing ontology: An EMMO-based semantic framework for representing knowledge in battery testing and battery quality control. *Computers in Industry* **164**, 104203 (2025).
29. Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology. <https://github.com/emmo-repo/EMMO> (2024).
30. The Battery 2030+ Roadmap. <https://battery2030.eu/research/roadmap/>.
31. The BIG-MAP EU project. <https://www.big-map.eu/>.
32. Battery Interface Genome - Materials Acceleration Platform | BIG-MAP | Project | Fact Sheet | H2020. *CORDIS | European Commission* <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/957189>.
33. Battery2030+ website. <https://battery2030.eu/>.
34. Battery Interface Ontology — BattInfo documentation. <https://big-map.github.io/BattINFO/index.html>.
35. W3C. *W3C* <https://www.w3.org/>.
36. Wikidata. https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page.
37. DBpedia Association website. <https://www.dbpedia.org/> (2025).
38. PubChem website. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>.
39. InChI Trust website. <https://www.inchi-trust.org/>.
40. CAS Registry website. <https://www.cas.org/cas-data/cas-registry>.
41. Schema.org website. <https://schema.org/>.

42. Introducing the Knowledge Graph: things, not strings. *Google*
<https://blog.google/products/search/introducing-knowledge-graph-things-not/> (2012).
43. Google. <https://www.google.com>.
44. Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure website. *Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure*
<https://www.psdia.ac.uk/>.
45. PSDI Metadata. <https://metadata.psdia.ac.uk/>.
46. DCAT-US Schema v1.1 (Project Open Data Metadata Schema) | resources.data.gov.
<https://resources.data.gov/resources/dcat-us/>.
47. Gregory, A. *et al.* WorldFAIR (D2.3) Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) (Report Synthesising Recommendations for Disciplines and Cross-Disciplinary Research Areas).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236871> (2024) doi:10.5281/zenodo.11236871.
48. SPARQL 1.1 Overview. <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-sparql11-overview-20130321/>.
49. Mai, H. T., Chu, C. X. & Paulheim, H. Do LLMs Really Adapt to Domains? An Ontology Learning Perspective. in *The Semantic Web – ISWC 2024* (eds Demartini, G. *et al.*) 126–143 (Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2025). doi:10.1007/978-3-031-77844-5_7.
50. Hila, A. The epistemological consequences of large language models: rethinking collective intelligence and institutional knowledge. *AI & Soc* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-025-02426-3> (2025) doi:10.1007/s00146-025-02426-3.
51. BatCAT project website. <https://www.nmbu.no/en/research/projects/batcat>.
52. Gartner Hype Cycle Research Methodology. *Gartner*
<https://www.gartner.com/en/research/methodologies/gartner-hype-cycle>.
53. Del Nostro, P., Goldbeck, G. & Toti, D. CHAMEO: An ontology for the harmonisation of materials characterisation methodologies. *Applied Ontology* **17**, 401–421 (2022).
54. I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. *GO FAIR* <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i1-metadata-use-formal-accessible-shared-broadly-applicable-language-knowledge-representation/>.
55. Robinson, J. 'AI will have a very large impact on chemistry': £100 million AI materials hub to be built in Liverpool. *Chemistry World* <https://www.chemistryworld.com/news/ai-will-have-a-very-large-impact-on-chemistry-100-million-ai-materials-hub-to-be-built-in-liverpool/4022532.article>.

56. MaterialsCommons4EU website. <https://materialscommons4.eu/>.

57. Semantic Partners - Knowledge Graph Consultancy. <https://www.semanticpartners.com>.